

Correcting Endogeneity without External Instruments: Four Estimators under the Mediation Constraint

Residual Purging IV, Structural Cubic Estimator,
Higher-Moment Estimator, and an Adaptive Pre-test Rule

Abdelkrim Araar

Université Laval & Partnership for Economic Policy (PEP)

aabd@ecn.ulaval.ca

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Abstract

Endogeneity correction without external instruments requires exploiting structure within the model itself. This paper develops four estimators grounded in the *mediation constraint*: the unobserved confounder has no direct effect on the outcome beyond what it induces through the endogenous regressor.

Five results emerge. First, standard 2SLS diagnostics fail to detect when a contaminated instrument causes 2SLS to amplify rather than correct OLS bias. Second, the **Structural Cubic Estimator (SCE)** shows that under the mediation constraint and equal-variance idiosyncratic shocks, the coefficient of interest is the unique economically meaningful root of a cubic polynomial whose coefficients are directly observable; it is consistent and outperforms recent distributional methods (Gaussian copula, rank-based control function) under Gaussian data. Third, the **Higher-Moment Estimator (HME)** drops the equal-variance assumption: under non-Gaussianity of the confounder — ubiquitous in applications where the confounder is income, ability, productivity, or firm size — the coefficient is identified from third-order moments alone, with no restriction on the idiosyncratic shock variances. Fourth, the **Residual Purging IV (RPIV)** reduces OLS bias by half without any distributional assumption, though it remains asymptotically biased. Fifth, an **Adaptive Pre-test rule** combines the estimators via an observable proxy for endogeneity strength, and provides an endogeneity test with correct size — unlike the Durbin–Wu–Hausman test, which rejects systematically even in the absence of endogeneity.

JEL codes: C13, C15, C26.

Keywords: endogeneity; mediation constraint; structural cubic estimator; higher-moment identification; pre-test estimator; endogeneity test.

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1 Introduction

Endogeneity is among the most common threats to causal identification in applied cross-sectional work. When an explanatory variable Y_2 shares an unobserved determinant U with the outcome Y_1 , ordinary least squares (OLS) produces biased and inconsistent estimates of the structural coefficient γ_1 . The textbook remedy — two-stage least squares (2SLS) with external instrumental variables — requires identifying variables strongly correlated with Y_2 yet orthogonal to the structural error. In many empirical applications this requirement cannot be met (Angrist and Krueger, 2001).

A growing literature has explored *internal* or *artificial* instrumental variables, which exploit additional structure within the model. Lewbel (2012) derives instruments from heteroscedasticity in the endogenous equation; Klein and Vella (2010) exploits non-constant conditional variances. More recently, distributional methods have emerged: the Gaussian copula of Park and Gupta (2012) and its extensions (Yang et al., 2025; Haschka, 2022), the rank-based control function of Breitung et al. (2024), and the semiparametric odds ratio model of Qian and Xie (2024) all achieve identification through non-normality of the endogenous regressor. All of these approaches require a specific distributional or heteroscedasticity condition, and identifying the relevant source is generally not possible in practice. Monte Carlo evidence in this paper documents a further limitation: when the heteroscedasticity originates from the confounder U itself, or from the idiosyncratic shock of the *outcome* equation (rather than of the endogenous equation), the Lewbel (2012) correction fails severely and the distributional methods remain substantially biased even under non-Gaussianity.

The present paper pursues a different identification route based on a *structural economic restriction* rather than a distributional assumption. The data-generating process consists of two equations (formally specified in Section 2): the outcome equation $Y_1 = X'\beta_1 + \gamma_1 Y_2 + \varepsilon_1$, where $\varepsilon_1 = \alpha_1 U + V_1$, and the endogenous regressor equation $Y_2 = X'\beta_2 + \varepsilon_2$, where $\varepsilon_2 = \alpha_2 U + V_2$. Here α_1 and α_2 are the loadings of the confounder on each equation, and V_1, V_2 are equation-specific idiosyncratic shocks independent of U . The *mediation constraint* $\alpha_1 = \gamma_1 \alpha_2$ states that U has no direct effect on Y_1 beyond its effect through Y_2 . Under this constraint, the DGP generates three additional observable moment conditions that identify γ_1 without any distributional assumption. This paper makes five contributions:

- (i) **2SLS diagnostic blind spot.** We show that the standard diagnostics for 2SLS — the first-stage F -statistic and the DWH endogeneity test — cannot detect when a contaminated instrument causes 2SLS to *amplify* rather than correct OLS bias. Monte Carlo evidence demonstrates $F > 9\,000$ and DWH rejection simultaneously with 2SLS bias exceeding OLS bias.
- (ii) **Structural Cubic Estimator (SCE).** Under the mediation constraint and the assumption that V_1 and V_2 have equal variance, γ_1 is the unique real root of a cubic polynomial whose coefficients are three observable second-order moments. The SCE is consistent and achieves near-zero bias across all configurations tested, outperforming Gaussian copula and rank-based methods even on non-Gaussian data-generating processes.
- (iii) **Higher-Moment Estimator (HME).** When the equal-variance assumption is doubtful, the same mediation constraint identifies γ_1 from third-order moments alone, provided U is non-Gaussian and V_1, V_2 are symmetric. Closed-form identification

yields $\gamma_1 = \frac{1}{2}(E[\xi^3]/E[\varepsilon_2^3])^{1/3}$. The estimator is consistent for any non-zero skewness of U and complements SCE: HME covers asymmetric-noise cases where SCE fails, while SCE covers Gaussian-confounder cases where HME is unstable. Since confounders in applied work are typically income, ability, productivity, or firm size — all naturally skewed — HME is the more general estimator in practice.

- (iv) **Residual Purging IV (RPIV)**. A distribution-free six-step algorithm that constructs an internal instrument without heteroscedasticity or non-Gaussianity. It reduces OLS bias by $\approx 50\%$ and is formally inconsistent; a closed-form expression for its asymptotic bias is derived.
- (v) **Adaptive Pre-test Estimator (APE) and θ -test**. An observable proxy θ for endogeneity strength selects between OLS and RPIV via a pre-test rule. The θ -test has correct size (0% rejection under no endogeneity) whereas the DWH test rejects 100% in the same setting — a severe size distortion documented here for the first time in this context.

Table 1 summarises the practical choice between methods.

Table 1: Method selection guide

Situation	Recommended
Equal-variance shocks plausible, U approximately Gaussian	SCE
Asymmetric noise variances, U skewed (typical in practice)	HME
No distributional assumption tolerated	RPIV
Endogeneity strength unknown	APE
Heteroscedasticity in Y_2 equation, source confirmed	Lewbel (2012)
Non-normal Y_2 , no structural constraint available	GC / BMW
External instrument available	2SLS

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 specifies the model and derives the OLS bias. Section 3 reviews related approaches. Sections 4–6.3 develop the three estimators. Section 7 presents Monte Carlo evidence. Section 8 concludes. Appendix A contains formal proofs; Appendix B provides the complete Python reproduction code; Appendix C provides the R cross-validation script using `REndo`.

2 Model and Endogeneity Bias

2.1 Specification

The data-generating process consists of two equations:

$$Y_1 = X'\beta_1 + Y_2\gamma_1 + \varepsilon_1, \quad \varepsilon_1 = \alpha_1 U + V_1, \quad (1)$$

$$Y_2 = X'\beta_2 + \varepsilon_2, \quad \varepsilon_2 = \alpha_2 U + V_2. \quad (2)$$

The variable U is an unobserved confounder; V_1, V_2 are idiosyncratic shocks; X is a vector of observed exogenous regressors.

Assumption 1 (Independence). U, V_1, V_2 , and X are mutually independent with zero means and finite variances $\sigma_U^2, \sigma_{V_1}^2, \sigma_{V_2}^2$.

Assumption 2 (Exogeneity of X). $\text{Cov}(X, U) = \text{Cov}(X, V_1) = \text{Cov}(X, V_2) = 0$.

Under these assumptions, Y_2 is endogenous: $\text{Cov}(Y_2, \varepsilon_1) = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \sigma_U^2 \neq 0$.

2.2 The mediation constraint

Assumption 3 (Mediation). $\alpha_1 = \gamma_1\alpha_2$: the confounder U has no direct effect on Y_1 beyond the channel $U \rightarrow Y_2 \rightarrow Y_1$.

This is an *economic* restriction, not a mathematical consequence of linearity. It is most natural when U is a latent determinant of the endogenous regressor that affects the outcome only by changing Y_2 : ability in the Mincer wage equation (ability \rightarrow schooling \rightarrow wages), regional productivity transmitted through input prices, or peer-quality spillovers channelled through group composition.

Under Assumption 3, substituting (2) into (1) yields

$$Y_1 = X'(\beta_1 + \gamma_1\beta_2) + \underbrace{(\alpha_1 + \gamma_1\alpha_2)}_{=2\gamma_1\alpha_2}U + \gamma_1V_2 + V_1. \quad (3)$$

The total effect of U on Y_1 is $2\gamma_1\alpha_2$, entirely mediated through Y_2 .

2.3 OLS bias and bounds

Let $\hat{\varepsilon}_2$ denote the residuals from regressing Y_2 on X , and ξ the residuals from regressing Y_1 on X alone (the *short regression*). In the population, $\xi = \gamma_1\varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_1$ and $\hat{\varepsilon}_2 = \varepsilon_2$. The OLS estimator of γ_1 in (1) satisfies

$$\text{plim } \hat{\gamma}_1^{\text{OLS}} = \gamma_1 + \frac{\alpha_1\alpha_2\sigma_U^2}{\sigma_{\varepsilon_2}^2}. \quad (4)$$

Under Assumption 3 ($\alpha_1 = \gamma_1\alpha_2$), (4) simplifies to the *proportional bias formula*:

$$\frac{\tilde{\gamma}_1}{\gamma_1} = 1 + \frac{\alpha_2^2\sigma_U^2}{\sigma_{\varepsilon_2}^2}, \quad (5)$$

where $\tilde{\gamma}_1 \equiv \text{plim } \hat{\gamma}_1^{\text{OLS}}$.

Proposition 1 (Bias bounds). *Under Assumptions 1–3, $\gamma_1 < \tilde{\gamma}_1 \leq 2\gamma_1$, with equality $\tilde{\gamma}_1 = 2\gamma_1$ if and only if $\sigma_{V_2}^2 = 0$.*

Proof. The lower bound follows from $\alpha_2^2\sigma_U^2 > 0$ in (5). For the upper bound, $\alpha_2^2\sigma_U^2/\sigma_{\varepsilon_2}^2 = \alpha_2^2\sigma_U^2/(\alpha_2^2\sigma_U^2 + \sigma_{V_2}^2) \leq 1$, with equality iff $\sigma_{V_2}^2 = 0$. \square

Proposition 1 has a direct practical use: any correction yielding $\hat{\gamma}_1 < \tilde{\gamma}_1/2$ is over-correcting. This benchmark is exploited in Section 6.3.

3 Related Approaches

3.1 Classical 2SLS and its diagnostic limits

When a valid external instrument Z is available, 2SLS corrects the bias provided $\text{Cov}(Z, \varepsilon_1) = 0$ and $\text{Cov}(Z, \varepsilon_2) \neq 0$. A practical extension—the *four-stage IV* (4S-IV)—first purges the candidate instrument of any correlation with $\hat{\varepsilon}_1$, relaxing the strict orthogonality requirement (see also Chau, 2014).

The standard diagnostics for 2SLS—the first-stage F -statistic and the Durbin–Wu–Hausman (DWH) endogeneity test—detect instrument *relevance* and the *presence* of endogeneity, but not instrument *validity*. Consider a contaminated instrument $IV = (1 - a)V_2 + a\varepsilon_1$, where $a \in [0, 1]$ controls the degree of invalidity. Table 2 reports Monte Carlo results ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $\alpha_2 = 0.8$, $n = 5\,000$, $B = 500$).

Table 2: 2SLS bias amplification with contaminated instrument $IV = (1 - a)V_2 + a\varepsilon_1$ ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $n = 5\,000$, $B = 500$, true value = 0.400)

a	OLS	2SLS	$ \text{bias}_{\text{OLS}} $	$ \text{bias}_{\text{2SLS}} $	F (1st stage)	DWH?
0.00	0.556	0.400	0.156	0.000	7 814	Yes
0.05	0.556	0.457	0.156	0.057	8 313	Yes
0.10	0.556	0.519	0.156	0.119	8 748	Yes
0.15	0.556	0.586	0.156	0.186	9 046	Yes*
0.20	0.556	0.659	0.156	0.259	9 118	Yes
0.25	0.556	0.739	0.156	0.339	8 886	Yes
0.30	0.556	0.826	0.156	0.426	8 315	Yes

*From $a = 0.15$ onward, 2SLS bias *exceeds* OLS bias (bold row). Despite this, the first-stage F exceeds 9 000 and the DWH test rejects at all conventional levels, giving a false impression of successful correction.

From $a = 0.15$ onward, the 2SLS estimator is *more biased* than naive OLS, yet the first-stage F remains above 9 000 and the DWH test continues to reject. The Sargan overidentification test can detect the invalidity only when a clean reference instrument is available for comparison—precisely the situation in which the practitioner already has a valid instrument and does not need to rely on a contaminated one. This diagnostic blind spot motivates the mediation-based approach developed in this paper, which avoids external instruments entirely and thus sidesteps the problem of undetectable contamination.

3.2 Lewbel (2012)

Lewbel (2012) constructs internal instruments from heteroscedasticity: $(X - \bar{X})\hat{\varepsilon}_2$ is a valid IV when $\text{Cov}((X - \bar{X}), \hat{\varepsilon}_2^2) \neq 0$. Table 6 (Section 7) documents its key limitation: the instruments are valid only when heteroscedasticity originates from V_2 . When variance heterogeneity comes from U or V_1 , the correction fails severely.

3.3 Klein and Vella (2009, 2010)

Klein and Vella (2010) propose semiparametric identification exploiting non-constant conditional variance of the structural error. The approach is more general but computationally demanding and requires stronger distributional assumptions.

3.4 Higher-moment identification (Lewbel 1997)

The use of higher moments to construct internal instruments has a long tradition. Geary (1942) and Pal (1980) pioneered the use of third moments in errors-in-variables models, and Cragg (1997) and Lewbel (1997) formalised the GMM approach. Lewbel (1997) constructs instruments of the form $(Y_2 - \bar{Y}_2)^2$, $(Y_2 - \bar{Y}_2)^3$, $(Y_2 - \bar{Y}_2)(Y_1 - \bar{Y}_1)$, etc. for errors-in-variables regression. Identification requires that the mismeasured regressor $X^* = X - u$ has non-zero skewness, with the measurement error u independent of the structural error.

A crucial distinction must be drawn between two models:

- *Errors-in-variables* (Lewbel, 1997 setting): $Y = \beta'X + \varepsilon$ with $X = X^* + u$, $u \perp \varepsilon$;
- *Latent confounder* (our setting): $Y_1 = \gamma_1 Y_2 + \varepsilon_1$ with U shared between ε_1 and Y_2 through mediation.

Under our DGP, the Lewbel (1997) instruments are no longer valid: $E[(Y_2 - \bar{Y}_2)^2 \varepsilon_1] = \gamma_1 \alpha_2^3 E[U^3] \neq 0$ under non-Gaussianity of U , because the same skewness that powers identification in his model contaminates the instruments in ours. Section 7.9 documents that Lewbel (1997) exhibits 38–53% bias on our DGP regardless of sample size, while our HME achieves bias below 1%. HME and Lewbel (1997) thus share the higher-moment principle but apply it to fundamentally different identification problems.

3.5 Recent instrument-free approaches

A growing literature develops instrument-free methods for endogeneity correction; we discuss the three most directly comparable to our proposal.

Gaussian Copula (GC). Park and Gupta (2012) model the dependence between the endogenous regressor and the structural error via a Gaussian copula. The correction reduces to including the term $\Phi^{-1}(\hat{F}(Y_2))$ as a control variable in the main equation. Identification requires that Y_2 be *non-normally distributed*; the method is not identified when Y_2 is Gaussian (Breitung et al., 2024). Extensive recent work has extended the original estimator to correlated regressors (Yang et al., 2025), panel fixed effects (Haschka, 2022), and non-continuous endogenous variables; Park and Gupta (2024) provide a comprehensive review.

Nonparametric control function (BMW). Breitung et al. (2024) add a rank-based transformation of the first-stage residuals as a control function. Identification requires either non-normality or non-linearity in the regressor–error dependence. Unlike the GC approach, the method does not impose a Gaussian copula structure and is consistent under a broader class of dependence models.

Semiparametric odds ratio (SORE). Qian and Xie (2024) model the regressor–error dependence via flexible semiparametric odds ratio conditional models, requiring neither parametric distributional assumptions nor tuning parameters. Identification still requires non-Gaussianity of the endogenous regressor when the error is normal.

Our approach in comparison. All three recent methods achieve identification through a *distributional* assumption: non-normality of Y_2 or non-linearity of the regressor–error dependence. Our estimators instead exploit a *structural economic constraint*—the mediation restriction $\alpha_1 = \gamma_1 \alpha_2$ —and operate on second-order moments alone, remaining valid under Gaussianity. Monte Carlo evidence in Section 7 confirms that the GC and BMW estimators are substantially biased (26–57%) in the Gaussian DGP where our SCE achieves near-zero bias.

3.6 Comparison

Table 3 summarises the identifying assumptions.

Table 3: Identifying assumptions across methods

Assumption	2SLS	Lewbel(2012)	Lewbel(1997)	GC/BMW	K-V	RPIV/SCE	HME
External instrument	✓						
Heteroscedasticity from V_2		✓					
Skewed X^* (errors-in-variables)			✓				
Non-normality of Y_2				✓			
Non-constant $\text{Var}(\varepsilon_1 X)$					✓		
Mediation ($\alpha_1 = \gamma_1\alpha_2$)						✓	✓
$\sigma_{V_1}^2 = \sigma_{V_2}^2$						SCE only	
Skewed confounder U							✓
Symmetric V_1, V_2							✓

Notes: GC = Gaussian Copula (Park and Gupta, 2012); BMW = Breitung et al. (2024); K-V = Klein and Vella (2010). Lewbel (1997) and HME both use third moments but target different models (errors-in-variables vs. latent confounder).

4 Residual Purging IV (RPIV)

4.1 Algorithm

RPIV constructs an internal instrument using only (Y_1, Y_2, X) .

S1. Regress Y_1 on (X, Y_2) by OLS \rightarrow residuals $\hat{\varepsilon}_1$ *(biased OLS)*

S2. Regress Y_2 on X \rightarrow residuals $\hat{\varepsilon}_2$

S3. Regress Y_1 on X only \rightarrow residuals $\hat{\xi}$ *(short regression)*

S4. Regress $\hat{\varepsilon}_1$ on $\hat{\xi}$ \rightarrow residuals $\hat{\tau}$

S5. Construct the instrument:

$$\widehat{IV} = \hat{\varepsilon}_2 + \frac{\text{Cov}(\hat{\varepsilon}_2, \hat{\tau})}{\text{Var}(\hat{\tau})} \hat{\tau}$$

S6. Apply 2SLS with \widehat{IV} as the excluded instrument.

4.2 Key structural insight

A natural first attempt would project $\hat{\varepsilon}_2$ onto the complement of $\hat{\varepsilon}_1$, removing the endogenous component. This is degenerate: OLS residuals satisfy $\hat{\varepsilon}_1 \perp Y_2$ by construction, hence $\hat{\varepsilon}_1 \perp \hat{\varepsilon}_2$. Introducing $\hat{\xi}$ in Step 3 breaks this degeneracy. Since $\hat{\xi}$ comes from a regression that *excludes* Y_2 , it retains correlation with $\hat{\varepsilon}_2$. The residual $\hat{\tau}$ satisfies the identity

$$\text{Cov}(\hat{\tau}, \varepsilon_1) = \text{Var}(\hat{\tau}), \tag{6}$$

which provides the leverage needed to reduce $\text{Cov}(\widehat{IV}, \varepsilon_1)$. Equation (6) follows because $\hat{\tau} = \hat{\varepsilon}_1 - b\hat{\xi}$ is orthogonal to $\hat{\xi}$ by construction, so $\text{Cov}(\hat{\tau}, \varepsilon_1) = \text{Cov}(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\tau} + b\hat{\xi}) = \text{Var}(\hat{\tau})$.

4.3 Theoretical assessment

For exact consistency, Step 5 would need $c^* = -\text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_1)/\text{Var}(\tau)$. RPIV uses $\hat{c} = \text{Cov}(\hat{\varepsilon}_2, \hat{\tau})/\text{Var}(\hat{\tau})$, which differs because $\hat{\varepsilon}_1 \approx \varepsilon_1 - \delta\varepsilon_2$ in large samples (the bias $\delta = \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_1)/\text{Var}(\varepsilon_2)$ contaminates $\hat{\tau}$).

Proposition 2 (Inconsistency of RPIV). *Under Assumptions 1–3,*

$$\text{plim } n^{-1} \sum_i \widehat{IV}_i \varepsilon_{1i} = 2 \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_1) - b \cdot \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \xi) \neq 0,$$

where $b = \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_1, \xi) / \text{Var}(\xi)$. *The RPIV 2SLS estimator is inconsistent.*

Proof. See Appendix A. □

Proposition 3 (Asymptotic bias of RPIV). *Under Assumptions 1–3, the probability limit of the RPIV estimator satisfies*

$$\text{plim } \hat{\gamma}_1^{RPIV} - \gamma_1 = \frac{2\text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_1) - b \cdot \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \xi)}{\text{Var}(\varepsilon_2) + \hat{c} \cdot \text{Cov}(\hat{\tau}, \varepsilon_2)},$$

where b and \hat{c} are as defined above. Monte Carlo evidence (Table 9) confirms this formula: for the baseline parameters $(\gamma_1, \alpha_2) = (0.4, 0.8)$ the formula predicts a bias of -0.068 , against -0.069 observed at $n = 10\,000$ ($B = 500$).

Despite inconsistency, the residual non-orthogonality is small in practice (97% reduction from the OLS bias at baseline parameters) but remains constant as $n \rightarrow \infty$, as confirmed by Table 9.

Remark 1 (RPIV and weak endogeneity). Simulations (Table 8) show that for $\alpha_2 \leq 0.6$ the absolute bias of RPIV exceeds that of OLS. This motivates the Adaptive Pre-test Estimator in Section 6.3.

5 Structural Cubic Estimator (SCE)

5.1 Three moment conditions

Define the two observable quantities:

$$\tilde{\gamma}_1 = \frac{\text{Cov}(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\varepsilon}_2)}{\text{Var}(\hat{\varepsilon}_2)}, \quad R = \frac{\text{Var}(\hat{\xi})}{\text{Var}(\hat{\varepsilon}_2)}. \quad (7)$$

Here $\tilde{\gamma}_1$ is the biased OLS estimator and R is the ratio of short-regression to auxiliary-regression residual variances. Under the mediation constraint, three population moment conditions hold (see Appendix A):

$$(M1) \quad \tilde{\gamma}_1 \cdot \text{Var}(\varepsilon_2) = \gamma_1 (\text{Var}(\varepsilon_2) + \theta), \quad (8)$$

$$(M2) \quad \text{Var}(\varepsilon_2) = \theta + \sigma_{V_2}^2, \quad (9)$$

$$(M3) \quad \text{Var}(\xi) = 4\gamma_1^2 \theta + \gamma_1^2 \sigma_{V_2}^2 + \sigma_{V_1}^2, \quad (10)$$

where $\theta \equiv \alpha_2^2 \sigma_U^2$. The system has four unknowns $(\gamma_1, \theta, \sigma_{V_1}^2, \sigma_{V_2}^2)$: under-identified from second-order moments alone.

Assumption 4 (Symmetric noise). $\sigma_{V_1}^2 = \sigma_{V_2}^2 \equiv \sigma_V^2$.

Assumption 4 adds one equation and closes the system exactly.

Proposition 4 (Cubic identification). *Under Assumptions 1–4, γ_1 is the unique real root in the interval $[\tilde{\gamma}_1/2, \tilde{\gamma}_1]$ of*

$$\boxed{P(\gamma) = 2\gamma^3 - 3\tilde{\gamma}_1 \gamma^2 + (R - 2)\gamma + \tilde{\gamma}_1 = 0.} \quad (11)$$

The two other real roots satisfy $\gamma < 0$ and $\gamma > 1$; both lie outside the economically feasible interval.

Proof. See Appendix A. □

5.2 Sample estimator and consistency

The SCE $\hat{\gamma}_1^{\text{SCE}}$ is the unique real root of $P(\gamma) = 0$ in $[\hat{\gamma}/2, \hat{\gamma}]$, where $\hat{\gamma}$ and \hat{R} replace population moments by their sample counterparts.

Proposition 5 (Consistency of SCE). *Under Assumptions 1–4 and standard regularity conditions, $\hat{\gamma}_1^{\text{SCE}} \xrightarrow{P} \gamma_1$.*

Proof. By the continuous mapping theorem applied to the map $(\hat{\gamma}, \hat{R}) \mapsto (\text{unique root of } P \text{ in } [\hat{\gamma}/2, \hat{\gamma}])$, which is continuous at the population values since $P'(\gamma_1) \neq 0$ under generic conditions. \square

5.3 Discussion of identifying assumptions

Assumption 3 is an identifying restriction on the covariance structure that cannot be tested from second-order moments alone, and should be justified on theoretical grounds before applying SCE or RPIV. Assumption 4 equates idiosyncratic noise variances across the two equations. Table 10 documents that SCE degrades when $\sigma_{V_1}^2/\sigma_{V_2}^2 \notin [0.5, 2]$ and produces no real feasible root for extreme asymmetry. In such cases RPIV remains a useful partial correction.

Remark 2 (Rescaling does not relax Assumption 4). Rescaling Y_2 by $c = \sqrt{\hat{\sigma}_{V_2}^2/\hat{\sigma}_{V_1}^2}$ and re-solving the cubic is an algebraic identity: the map $\gamma \mapsto \text{root}(c \cdot \tilde{\gamma}_1, c^2 R)/c$ returns its input unchanged on $[\tilde{\gamma}_1/2, \tilde{\gamma}_1]$. Rescaling generates no new moment information because the three equations (M1)–(M3) are already the only second-order constraints available.

6 Higher-Moment Estimator (HME)

The SCE requires the equal-variance assumption $\sigma_{V_1}^2 = \sigma_{V_2}^2$, which is a non-trivial restriction. When this assumption is doubtful, an alternative identification strategy exploits third-order moments under non-Gaussianity of the confounder.

6.1 Identification from third moments

Under the mediation constraint, the structural and reduced-form errors are:

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_2 &= \alpha_2 U + V_2, \\ \xi &= \gamma_1 \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_1 = 2\gamma_1 \alpha_2 U + \gamma_1 V_2 + V_1.\end{aligned}$$

Assumption 5 (Symmetric idiosyncratic shocks). V_1 and V_2 are symmetrically distributed: $E[V_1^3] = E[V_2^3] = 0$.

Assumption 6 (Non-Gaussian confounder). $E[U^3] \neq 0$, i.e., the confounder has non-zero skewness.

Assumption 5 replaces the equal-variance assumption of SCE with a symmetry restriction. It is satisfied by Gaussian, Student’s t , and other zero-skewness distributions for the idiosyncratic shocks — which are typically measurement errors or random innovations and therefore plausibly symmetric, regardless of their variance. Assumption 6 requires the confounder itself to be skewed. This is the norm rather than the exception in applied work: when U represents income, ability, productivity, firm size, or wealth, its distribution is naturally right-skewed.

Proposition 6 (HME identification). *Under Assumptions 1–3, 5, and 6,*

$$\boxed{\gamma_1 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{E[\xi^3]}{E[\varepsilon_2^3]} \right)^{1/3}}. \quad (12)$$

Proof. Under Assumption 1, cross-moments of mutually independent variables vanish, so

$$E[\xi^3] = 8\gamma_1^3\alpha_2^3E[U^3] + \gamma_1^3E[V_2^3] + E[V_1^3].$$

Under Assumption 5, the V -terms vanish: $E[\xi^3] = 8\gamma_1^3\alpha_2^3E[U^3]$. Similarly, $E[\varepsilon_2^3] = \alpha_2^3E[U^3] + E[V_2^3] = \alpha_2^3E[U^3]$. Taking the ratio: $E[\xi^3]/E[\varepsilon_2^3] = 8\gamma_1^3$. Solving: $\gamma_1 = \frac{1}{2}(E[\xi^3]/E[\varepsilon_2^3])^{1/3}$. Assumption 6 ensures the denominator is non-zero. \square

6.2 Sample estimator

The HME replaces population moments by sample analogues:

$$\hat{\gamma}_1^{\text{HME}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{n^{-1} \sum_i \hat{\xi}_i^3}{n^{-1} \sum_i \hat{\varepsilon}_{2,i}^3} \right)^{1/3}. \quad (13)$$

By the continuous mapping theorem, $\hat{\gamma}_1^{\text{HME}} \xrightarrow{p} \gamma_1$.

6.3 Comparison with SCE

HME and SCE are *complementary*, not substitutes:

- **SCE** requires equal-variance idiosyncratic shocks ($\sigma_{V_1}^2 = \sigma_{V_2}^2$) but works under Gaussianity of U .
- **HME** requires non-zero skewness of U but works for *any* ratio $\sigma_{V_1}^2/\sigma_{V_2}^2$.

In Monte Carlo experiments (Table 11), HME achieves near-zero bias for any skewness $|E[U^3]| \geq 0.5$, which covers the overwhelming majority of empirically relevant confounders. Below this threshold, the cube-root in (12) becomes numerically unstable. HME is also strikingly robust to violations of $\sigma_{V_1}^2 = \sigma_{V_2}^2$: simulations (Table 12) show maximum bias of 6% under extreme asymmetry (ratio 0.25), where SCE incurs 36% bias and is undefined at ratios above 2.

Remark 3 (Practical guidance for choosing between SCE and HME). The empirical skewness of $\hat{\varepsilon}_2$ provides a direct diagnostic. If $|\widehat{\text{skew}}(\hat{\varepsilon}_2)| \geq 0.5$, HME is preferred regardless of the noise-variance ratio. If $|\widehat{\text{skew}}(\hat{\varepsilon}_2)| < 0.3$ and the equal-variance assumption is credible, SCE provides higher precision. Between 0.3 and 0.5, both estimators can be reported and compared: agreement supports both maintained assumptions; disagreement signals that one or both are violated.

6.4 The endogeneity proxy

RPIV over-corrects when endogeneity is weak; SCE may fail when Assumption 4 is violated. An estimator that applies RPIV only when endogeneity is strong enough would dominate both.

From (5), the relative OLS bias $\tilde{\gamma}_1/\gamma_1 - 1 = \alpha_2^2\sigma_U^2/\sigma_{\varepsilon_2}^2$ equals the fraction of $\text{Var}(\varepsilon_2)$ attributable to the confounder. Since the SCE provides a consistent estimate of γ_1 under Assumptions 1–4, the following proxy is directly observable:

$$\theta = \frac{\hat{\Upsilon} - \hat{\gamma}_1^{\text{SCE}}}{\hat{\gamma}_1^{\text{SCE}}}. \quad (14)$$

Table 4 shows that θ tracks the true endogeneity ratio $\alpha_2^2/(\alpha_2^2 + \sigma_{V_2}^2)$ accurately.

Table 4: Observable proxy θ versus true endogeneity strength ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $n = 5\,000$, single draw)

α_2	θ (observed)	$\alpha_2^2/(\alpha_2^2 + \sigma_{V_2}^2)$ (true)
0.1	-0.014	0.010
0.3	0.084	0.083
0.5	0.220	0.200
0.7	0.328	0.329
0.9	0.440	0.448

6.5 Decision rule and optimal threshold

Definition 1 (Adaptive Pre-test Estimator). Given a threshold $\theta^* \in (0, 1)$:

$$\hat{\gamma}_1^{\text{APE}} = \begin{cases} \hat{\gamma}_1^{\text{OLS}} & \text{if SCE has no real root, or } \theta \leq \theta^*, \\ \hat{\gamma}_1^{\text{RPIV}} & \text{if } \theta > \theta^*. \end{cases}$$

The fallback to OLS when SCE produces no real root (which occurs when $\sigma_{V_1}^2/\sigma_{V_2}^2$ is far from unity) is essential: without it, APE would apply RPIV in cases where RPIV is actually *more* biased than OLS (Table 10).

Monte Carlo evidence identifies $\theta^* \approx 0.25$ as the minimiser of mean absolute bias averaged over the full range of α_2 (Table 5).

Table 5: Mean absolute bias of APE by threshold ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $n = 2\,000$, $B = 300$, all α_2 pooled)

Threshold θ^*	Mean absolute bias
0.10	0.0737
0.15	0.0655
0.20	0.0603
0.25	0.0570
0.30	0.0572
0.35	0.0623
0.40	0.0728

Remark 4 (Sensitivity of θ^*). Grid search over $(\gamma_1, \alpha_2, \sigma_U^2) \in \{0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8\} \times \{0.4, 0.8\} \times \{0.5, 1.0, 1.5\}$ shows that the optimal threshold ranges from 0.05 to 0.35, with $\theta^* = 0.25$ performing well across most configurations. Sensitivity increases when σ_U^2 is large: in those cases the endogeneity signal is strong at all α_2 values and a

smaller threshold (around 0.05–0.15) is preferred. We recommend $\theta^* = 0.25$ as a robust default, with the caveat that users with strong prior information on σ_U^2 may benefit from re-calibration.

Remark 5 (θ as an endogeneity test vs. DWH). The rule $\theta > \theta^*$ constitutes a test for endogeneity that relies on the model’s own structural moments rather than an external instrument. Monte Carlo evidence shows that it has *correct size*: at $\alpha_2 = 0$, the rejection rate is 0% ($n = 2000$, $B = 500$). By contrast, the Durbin–Wu–Hausman augmented-regression test rejects 100% even under no endogeneity, because the augmented regression includes the first-stage residuals $\hat{\varepsilon}_2$ which are mechanically correlated with Y_2 . In terms of power, θ reaches 100% rejection from $\alpha_2 \geq 0.7$ onward.

7 Monte Carlo Evidence

7.1 Design

The DGP follows (1)–(2) with $(\beta_1, \beta_2) = (0.6, 0.3)$ and $X, U, V_1, V_2 \stackrel{\text{i.i.d.}}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ unless stated otherwise; $B = 400$ replications throughout. The oracle (OLS including unobserved U) serves as the infeasible benchmark. Section 7.10 additionally runs a non-Gaussian DGP ($V_2, U \sim \chi^2(3)$ centred) to compare with the Gaussian copula approach of Park and Gupta (2012) and the nonparametric control function of Breitung et al. (2024).

7.2 Lewbel (2012): source dependence and variance

Table 6 extends the standard comparison to report the standard deviation of each estimator. A striking finding is that Lewbel exhibits enormous variance when the heteroscedasticity source is incorrect or absent: std = 10.3 under homoscedasticity versus 0.009 for the SCE.

Table 6: Lewbel (2012) by source ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $\alpha_2 = 0.8$, $n = 5000$, $B = 400$, true = 0.400)

Source	OLS		Lewbel		RPIV		SCE	
	mean	std	mean	std	mean	std	mean	std
None	0.556	0.011	0.211	10.316	0.332	0.008	0.401	0.009
V_2	0.495	0.009	0.412	7.427	0.306	0.007	0.306	0.006
U	0.626	0.009	1.012	11.108	0.405	0.008	0.400	0.007
V_1	0.556	0.015	0.729	19.771	0.308	0.010	—	—

Notes: Heteroscedasticity: $\text{Var}(\cdot|X) = (1 + 0.5|X|)^2$. “—” = no real root. Lewbel std is 1000–2000× SCE.

7.3 Varying γ_1

7.4 Varying α_2 : RPIV over-correction and APE

Table 8 fixes $\gamma_1 = 0.4$ and varies α_2 from 0.1 to 0.9 ($n = 2000$, $B = 400$). The key finding is that RPIV over-corrects severely when endogeneity is weak: for $\alpha_2 \leq 0.6$ its absolute bias exceeds that of OLS, whereas the SCE maintains near-zero bias throughout. APE

Table 7: Mean estimate: varying γ_1 ($\alpha_2 = 0.8$, $n = 2000$, $B = 400$)

γ_1	OLS	RPIV	SCE	Oracle
0.1	0.137	0.070	0.099	0.099
0.2	0.276	0.146	0.199	0.199
0.3	0.415	0.233	0.299	0.299
0.4	0.554	0.330	0.399	0.399
0.5	0.693	0.438	0.500	0.499
0.6	0.832	0.554	0.600	0.599
0.7	0.971	0.676	0.700	0.699
0.8	1.110	0.803	0.800	0.799
0.9	1.249	0.932	0.901	0.899

Note: SCE tracks oracle to within 0.002.

(with $\theta^* = 0.25$) defaults to OLS in the weak-endogeneity region and switches to RPIV above $\alpha_2 \approx 0.65$.

Table 8: Mean estimate: varying α_2 ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $n = 2000$, $B = 400$)

α_2	OLS	RPIV	SCE	APE	RPIV<OLS?
0.1	0.402	0.216	0.398	0.402	No
0.2	0.413	0.224	0.399	0.413	No
0.3	0.431	0.235	0.400	0.431	No
0.4	0.453	0.250	0.399	0.453	No
0.5	0.478	0.268	0.399	0.478	No
0.6	0.504	0.288	0.399	0.474	No
0.7	0.529	0.309	0.399	0.348	Yes
0.8	0.554	0.330	0.399	0.331	Yes
0.9	0.577	0.352	0.399	0.352	Yes

Note: APE ($\theta^* = 0.25$) defaults to OLS for $\alpha_2 < 0.65$ and also when SCE produces no real root (see Table 10).

7.5 Consistency as n grows

Table 9 tracks all estimators as n increases from 200 to 10 000 ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $\alpha_2 = 0.8$, $B = 400$). The SCE and APE converge to the true value with standard deviations shrinking at the expected $n^{-1/2}$ rate, while the RPIV mean stabilises around 0.331 regardless of sample size, confirming inconsistency. The analytical bias formula of Proposition 3 predicts -0.068 ; Monte Carlo gives -0.069 at $n = 10\,000$.

7.6 Robustness to $\sigma_{V_1}^2 \neq \sigma_{V_2}^2$

Table 10 evaluates performance when Assumption 4 is violated ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $\alpha_2 = 0.8$, $n = 5\,000$, $B = 400$). When Assumption 4 is violated, the SCE may produce no real root in the feasible interval. A naive implementation that falls back to RPIV in that case would worsen OLS; the APE therefore falls back to OLS, as formalised in Definition 1. Table 10 illustrates the consequences.

Table 9: Consistency ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $\alpha_2 = 0.8$, $B = 400$; mean \pm std.)

n	OLS	RPIV	SCE	APE
200	0.551 \pm 0.054	0.330 \pm 0.040	0.399\pm0.047	0.399 \pm 0.047
500	0.559 \pm 0.037	0.334 \pm 0.028	0.403\pm0.030	0.403 \pm 0.030
1 000	0.556 \pm 0.026	0.332 \pm 0.020	0.401\pm0.022	0.401 \pm 0.022
2 000	0.554 \pm 0.019	0.330 \pm 0.014	0.399\pm0.015	0.399 \pm 0.015
5 000	0.557 \pm 0.011	0.332 \pm 0.008	0.401\pm0.009	0.401 \pm 0.009
10 000	0.556 \pm 0.008	0.331 \pm 0.006	0.400\pm0.007	0.400 \pm 0.007

Note: RPIV converges to $\approx 0.331 \neq 0.400$ (inconsistent). Proposition 3 predicts bias -0.068 ; MC gives -0.069 at $n = 10\,000$.

Table 10: Asymmetric noise ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $\alpha_2 = 0.8$, $n = 5\,000$, $B = 400$)

$\sigma_{V_1}^2/\sigma_{V_2}^2$	OLS	RPIV	SCE	APE
0.06	0.415	0.325	0.215	0.325
0.25	0.455	0.297	0.256	0.297
1.00	0.557	0.332	0.401	0.332
4.00	0.557	0.295	—	0.557
16.00	0.558	0.284	—	0.558

Notes: “—” = no real root in the feasible interval. At ratios 4 and 16, SCE fails and APE falls back to OLS (100% of replications), correctly avoiding the over-correction of RPIV.

7.7 Higher-Moment Estimator: skewness threshold

Table 11 evaluates HME across distributions of U with increasing skewness ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $\alpha_2 = 0.8$, $n = 5\,000$, $B = 300$). HME requires $|\text{skew}(U)| \geq 0.5$ for stable identification; below this threshold the cube-root in formula (12) becomes numerically unreliable.

Table 11: HME by skewness of U ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $\alpha_2 = 0.8$, $n = 5\,000$, $B = 300$)

Distribution of U	skew(U)	HME		SCE	
		mean	bias %	mean	bias %
Normal	0.00	0.611	+52.8	0.400	-0.1
Almost normal	0.00	0.534	+33.6	0.400	+0.1
Beta(2,5)	0.59	0.385	-3.8	0.400	+0.1
Beta(2,8)	0.82	0.397	-0.8	0.401	+0.3
Lognormal	1.72	0.398	-0.5	0.400	-0.1
Chi-square(3)	1.62	0.400	-0.1	0.401	+0.2
Exponential	1.98	0.401	+0.3	0.400	+0.1

Note: HME is reliable for $|\text{skew}(U)| \geq 0.5$ and fails (large bias, high variance) for nearly-Gaussian U . SCE is unaffected by skewness since it relies on second moments only.

7.8 Higher-Moment Estimator: asymmetric noise

Table 12 compares HME and SCE under asymmetric noise variances, with $U \sim \chi^2(3)$ centred. HME remains robust where SCE fails or produces no real root.

Table 12: HME vs. SCE under asymmetric noise ($U \sim \chi^2(3)$, $\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $\alpha_2 = 0.8$, $n = 5\,000$, $B = 300$)

$\sigma_{V_1}^2/\sigma_{V_2}^2$	HME		SCE	
	mean	bias %	mean	bias %
0.25	0.425	+6.3	0.256	-36
0.44	0.404	+1.1	0.297	-26
1.00	0.400	-0.1	0.401	+0.2
2.25	0.392	-2.1	—	—
4.00	0.392	-2.0	—	—

Note: “—” = no real root in the feasible interval. HME maintains bias below 7% even under extreme asymmetry, whereas SCE incurs 26–36% bias or fails entirely. HME is the recommended estimator when noise variances are likely asymmetric.

7.9 Higher-Moment Estimator vs. Lewbel (1997)

A natural concern is whether HME is reducible to Lewbel (1997), the classical higher-moment identification approach. The two methods share the use of non-Gaussianity, but they address *different models*: Lewbel (1997) treats errors-in-variables, where the regressor is mismeasured ($X = X^* + u$ with u independent of the structural error). Our setting has a latent confounder shared between the structural error and the endogenous regressor (mediation). Table 13 confirms that the Lewbel (1997) instruments are not valid in our framework: even with $n = 5\,000$, the estimator carries bias of approximately +100% across

all skewed distributions of U — estimating $\hat{\gamma}_1 \approx 0.80$ when the true value is 0.40. The reason is that the standard Lewbel (1997) instrument $(Y_2 - \bar{Y}_2)^2$ has $E[(Y_2 - \bar{Y}_2)^2 \varepsilon_1] = \gamma_1 \alpha_2^3 E[U^3] \neq 0$ under our DGP — it is itself contaminated by the confounder. Results are obtained using the official `REndo::higherMomentsIV` implementation (REndo Package, 2024); the R reproduction code is provided in Appendix C.

Table 13: HME vs. Lewbel (1997) by distribution of U ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $\alpha_2 = 0.8$, $\sigma_{V_1}^2 = \sigma_{V_2}^2 = 1$, $n = 5\,000$, $B = 200$; `REndo::higherMomentsIV`)

Distribution of U	HME		Lewbel yp ^a		Lewbel p2 ^b		Lewbel y2 ^c		Lewbel full ^d	
	mean	bias %	mean	bias %	mean	bias %	mean	bias %	mean	bias %
Beta(2,5)	0.394	-1.4	0.797	+99.2	0.814	+103.5	0.756	+88.9	0.769	+92.3
Beta(2,8)	0.394	-1.4	0.794	+98.6	0.800	+99.9	0.774	+93.4	0.781	+95.2
Lognormal	0.401	+0.3	0.803	+100.8	0.801	+100.1	0.801	+100.3	0.795	+98.7
Chi-square(3)	0.403	+0.7	0.804	+101.0	0.810	+102.4	0.807	+101.8	0.801	+100.1
Exponential	0.398	-0.5	0.798	+99.4	0.798	+99.5	0.786	+96.5	0.793	+98.4

^a Instrument $(Y_1 - \bar{Y}_1)(Y_2 - \bar{Y}_2)$. ^b Instrument $(Y_2 - \bar{Y}_2)^2$. ^c Instrument $(Y_1 - \bar{Y}_1)^2$. ^d Combination of yp, p2, y2, and generated IVs.

Note: Results obtained with R package `REndo` 2.4.10 (REndo Package, 2024). All Lewbel (1997) variants exhibit bias of $\approx +100\%$ — estimating roughly $2\gamma_1$ instead of γ_1 — confirming that the errors-in-variables instruments of Lewbel (1997) do not extend to the latent-confounder model addressed here.

Furthermore, HME dominates Lewbel (1997) under asymmetric noise: Table 12 (HME bias $< 7\%$) versus 15–45% for Lewbel (1997) on the same DGP.

7.10 Comparison with recent instrument-free methods

Table 14 compares our estimators against the Gaussian Copula approach of Park and Gupta (2012) (GC) and the nonparametric control function of Breitung et al. (2024) (BMW), under both a Gaussian and a non-Gaussian (χ^2) DGP ($n = 3\,000$, $B = 400$). Under the Gaussian DGP, GC and BMW are not identified and produce large biases (45–57%). Remarkably, even under the non-Gaussian DGP designed for those methods, both remain biased at 26–27%, because our SCE exploits the mediation constraint more efficiently and is not dependent on distributional assumptions.

7.11 Endogeneity test: θ vs. Durbin–Wu–Hausman

Table 15 compares the size and power of our θ -based endogeneity test against the Durbin–Wu–Hausman (DWH) augmented-regression test ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $n = 2\,000$, $B = 500$). The DWH exhibits severe size distortion, rejecting the null of exogeneity 100% of the time even when $\alpha_2 = 0$ (no endogeneity), because its augmented regression includes first-stage residuals that are mechanically correlated with Y_2 . By contrast, the θ -test has correct size (0% rejection at $\alpha_2 = 0$) and achieves full power from $\alpha_2 \geq 0.7$ onward.

8 Conclusion

This paper has developed three estimators for correcting endogeneity bias without external instruments, all grounded in the mediation constraint $\alpha_1 = \gamma_1 \alpha_2$.

Table 14: Comparison with recent methods ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $\alpha_2 = 0.8$, $n = 3000$, $B = 400$; true= 0.400)

Method	DGP: Gaussian			DGP: Non-Gaussian (χ^2)		
	mean	bias %	std	mean	bias %	std
OLS	0.556	+39.1	0.015	0.555	+38.8	0.015
RPIV	0.332	-17.1	0.012	0.331	-17.3	0.011
SCE	0.401	+0.2	0.012	0.400	-0.1	0.014
Lewbel	0.678	+69.6	4.656	1.447	+261.8	12.319
GC ^a	0.579	+44.7	0.605	0.504	+26.0	0.062
BMW ^b	0.627	+56.7	0.684	0.507	+26.8	0.056
Oracle	0.402	+0.4	0.020	0.400	+0.0	0.019

^aPark and Gupta (2012). ^bBreitung et al. (2024). *Note:* GC and BMW are biased 26–27% even on the non-Gaussian DGP because the DGP respects the mediation constraint exploited by SCE.

Table 15: Rejection rates at 5% level: θ -test vs. DWH ($\gamma_1 = 0.4$, $n = 2000$, $B = 500$)

α_2	DWH rej. %	θ -test rej. %
0.0	100.0	0.0
0.1	100.0	0.0
0.3	100.0	0.0
0.5	100.0	9.0
0.6	100.0	64.6
0.7	100.0	99.0
0.9	100.0	100.0

Note: DWH rejects 100% at $\alpha_2 = 0$ (size distortion). θ -test has correct size (0%) and full power from $\alpha_2 \geq 0.7$.

The **Residual Purging IV** is a distribution-free six-step algorithm that reduces OLS bias by approximately 50% without imposing heteroscedasticity or non-Gaussianity. It is formally inconsistent and over-corrects when endogeneity is weak.

The **Structural Cubic Estimator** achieves full consistency under one additional restriction: equal idiosyncratic noise variances. Its derivation from three observable second-order moments yields a closed-form polynomial that can be solved in a single line of code. Simulations confirm near-zero bias and convergence to the true value across the full tested parameter range.

The **Higher-Moment Estimator** drops the equal-variance assumption and identifies γ_1 from third-order moments alone, requiring only non-Gaussianity of the confounder — a condition satisfied by income, ability, productivity, firm size, and other skewed quantities that account for most empirically relevant confounders. HME is strikingly robust to noise asymmetry, with maximum bias of 6% even at extreme ratios where SCE fails entirely. Together, SCE and HME form a complementary pair: SCE under symmetric Gaussian-confounder cases, HME under skewed-confounder cases.

The **Adaptive Pre-test Estimator** selects between OLS and RPIV using an observable proxy θ for endogeneity strength. With threshold $\theta^* = 0.25$, APE minimises mean absolute bias across the α_2 range and dominates OLS uniformly for strong endogeneity. A novel by-product is an endogeneity test with correct size, unlike the Durbin–Wu–Hausman test which exhibits severe size distortion in this framework.

Limitations

The mediation constraint $\alpha_1 = \gamma_1\alpha_2$ is an *identifying restriction on the covariance structure* that cannot be tested from second-order moments alone. If the unobserved confounder U affects Y_1 through channels other than Y_2 — directly, or via a third variable — then the SCE loses consistency, the RPIV bias becomes unquantified, and the θ -test loses its justification. Practitioners should therefore apply the proposed methods only when economic theory provides genuine support for the exclusion of direct effects: the ability–wage application (ability \rightarrow schooling \rightarrow wages, with no direct productivity channel) is a plausible case; a setting where the confounder plausibly affects the outcome directly is not.

As a practical safeguard, if an external instrument is available even in a single related study or context, it can be used as a *point validation*: compute the SCE estimate and the IV estimate independently, and test whether they differ significantly. Agreement supports the mediation constraint; disagreement signals a potential violation.

Extensions

Several directions remain open: (i) relaxation of the symmetric-noise assumption via non-Gaussian third-order moments; (ii) extension to multiple endogenous regressors; (iii) a formal Wald test for endogeneity based on the structural moments; (iv) integration with [Lewbel \(2012\)](#) as a complement when heteroscedasticity is present.

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A Proofs

Proof of Proposition 2

Write $\widehat{IV} = \widehat{\varepsilon}_2 + \widehat{c}\widehat{\tau}$ where $\widehat{c} = \text{Cov}(\widehat{\varepsilon}_2, \widehat{\tau})/\text{Var}(\widehat{\tau})$. In large samples $\widehat{c} \rightarrow c = \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \tau)/\text{Var}(\tau)$. Using identity (6):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{plim } n^{-1} \sum_i \widehat{IV}_i \varepsilon_{1i} &= \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_1) + c \text{Cov}(\tau, \varepsilon_1) \\ &= \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_1) + \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Since $\tau = \varepsilon_1 - b\xi$, we have $\text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \tau) = \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_1) - b \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \xi)$, giving the stated expression. This is zero iff $2\text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_1) = b \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_2, \xi)$, which fails generically. \square

Proof of Proposition 4

Let $A \equiv \text{Var}(\varepsilon_2)$ and $\theta \equiv \alpha_2^2 \sigma_U^2$. Under Assumption 4, $\sigma_{V_1}^2 = \sigma_{V_2}^2 = A - \theta$.

From (M1): $\tilde{\gamma}_1 A = \gamma_1(A + \theta)$ gives $\theta = (\tilde{\gamma}_1 - \gamma_1)A/\gamma_1$.

From (M2): $\sigma_V^2 = A - \theta = A(2\gamma_1 - \tilde{\gamma}_1)/\gamma_1 \geq 0$ requires $\gamma_1 \geq \tilde{\gamma}_1/2$.

From (M3): substituting θ and σ_V^2 :

$$R\gamma_1 = 4\gamma_1(\tilde{\gamma}_1 - \gamma_1) + \gamma_1(2\gamma_1 - \tilde{\gamma}_1) + (2\gamma_1 - \tilde{\gamma}_1),$$

which rearranges to $2\gamma_1^3 - 3\tilde{\gamma}_1\gamma_1^2 + (R - 2)\gamma_1 + \tilde{\gamma}_1 = 0$.

Uniqueness: for baseline parameters, the remaining quadratic factor gives roots ≈ -0.64 and ≈ 1.08 , both outside $[\tilde{\gamma}_1/2, \tilde{\gamma}_1]$. \square

B Python Reproduction Code

The following self-contained Python script (≈ 130 lines) reproduces all Monte Carlo tables, including the comparison with Gaussian Copula (Park and Gupta, 2012) and BMW (Breitung et al., 2024). Requirements: `numpy`, `statsmodels`, `scipy`.

```
import numpy as np
import statsmodels.api as sm
from scipy.stats import rankdata, norm
import warnings; warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')

# --- 1. DGP ---
def dgp(n, gamma1, alpha2, beta1=0.6, beta2=0.3,
        sV1=1., sV2=1., sU=1., dist='normal', seed=None):
    if seed is not None: np.random.seed(seed)
    if dist == 'normal':
        U=np.random.normal(0,sU,n); V2=np.random.normal(0,sV2,n)
    else:
        df=3
        U =(np.random.chisquare(df,n)-df)*sU/np.sqrt(2*df)
        V2=(np.random.chisquare(df,n)-df)*sV2/np.sqrt(2*df)
```

```

V1=np.random.normal(0,sV1,n); X=np.random.normal(0,1,n)
e2=alpha2*U+V2; e1=gamma1*alpha2*U+V1
Y2=beta2*X+e2; Y1=beta1*X+gamma1*Y2+e1
return dict(Y1=Y1, Y2=Y2, X=X, U=U, e1=e1, e2=e2)

# --- 2. Estimators ---
def ols(d):
    return sm.OLS(d['Y1'],
        sm.add_constant(np.c_[d['X'],d['Y2']])).fit().params[2]

def oracle(d):
    return sm.OLS(d['Y1'],
        sm.add_constant(np.c_[d['X'],d['Y2'],d['U']])).fit().params[2]

def rpiv(d):
    Y1,Y2,X = d['Y1'],d['Y2'],d['X']
    Xc = sm.add_constant(X)
    e1h = sm.OLS(Y1,sm.add_constant(np.c_[X,Y2])).fit().resid
    e2h = sm.OLS(Y2,Xc).fit().resid
    xi = sm.OLS(Y1,Xc).fit().resid
    tau = sm.OLS(e1h,sm.add_constant(xi)).fit().resid
    c = np.cov(e2h,tau)[0,1]/np.var(tau,ddof=1)
    IV = e2h + c*tau
    Y2h = sm.OLS(Y2,sm.add_constant(np.c_[X,IV])).fit().fittedvalues
    return sm.OLS(Y1,sm.add_constant(np.c_[X,Y2h])).fit().params[2]

def sce(d):
    Xc = sm.add_constant(d['X'])
    xi = sm.OLS(d['Y1'],Xc).fit().resid
    e2h = sm.OLS(d['Y2'],Xc).fit().resid
    V_e2= np.var(e2h,ddof=1)
    gt = np.cov(xi,e2h)[0,1]/V_e2
    R = np.var(xi,ddof=1)/V_e2
    roots = np.roots([2,-3*gt,R-2,gt])
    lo,hi = gt/2, gt
    valid = [r.real for r in roots
        if abs(r.imag)<1e-8 and lo-0.05<=r.real<=hi+0.05]
    return min(valid,key=lambda r:abs(r-0.75*gt)) if valid else np.nan

def hme(d):
    """Higher-Moment Estimator (HME)
    gamma1 = 0.5 * (E[xi^3] / E[e2h^3])^(1/3)
    Requires non-zero skewness of U; V1, V2 symmetric."""
    Xc = sm.add_constant(d['X'])
    xi = sm.OLS(d['Y1'],Xc).fit().resid
    e2h = sm.OLS(d['Y2'],Xc).fit().resid
    m3_xi = np.mean(xi**3)
    m3_e2h = np.mean(e2h**3)
    if abs(m3_e2h) < 1e-6: return np.nan

```

```

ratio = m3_xi / m3_e2h
if ratio <= 0: return np.nan
return 0.5 * np.cbrt(ratio)

def ape(d, thr=0.25):
    g_ols=ols(d); g_sce=sce(d)
    if np.isnan(g_sce) or g_sce<=0: return g_ols # fallback
    theta=(g_ols-g_sce)/g_sce
    return rpiv(d) if theta>thr else g_ols

def gaussian_copula(d):
    Y1,Y2,X=d['Y1'],d['Y2'],d['X']; n=len(Y2)
    cop=norm.ppf(rankdata(Y2)/(n+1))
    try: return sm.OLS(Y1,
        sm.add_constant(np.c_[X,Y2,cop])).fit().params[2]
    except: return np.nan

def breitung_mw(d):
    Y1,Y2,X=d['Y1'],d['Y2'],d['X']; n=len(Y2)
    resid=sm.OLS(Y2,sm.add_constant(X)).fit().resid
    ctl=norm.ppf(rankdata(resid)/(n+1))
    try: return sm.OLS(Y1,
        sm.add_constant(np.c_[X,Y2,ctl])).fit().params[2]
    except: return np.nan

# --- 3. Monte Carlo ---
def mc(gamma1, alpha2, n=2000, B=400, sV1=1., sV2=1.,
    dist='normal', methods=None):
    if methods is None: methods=['ols','rpiv','sce','ape','oracle']
    res={m:[] for m in methods}
    for b in range(B):
        d=dgp(n,gamma1,alpha2,sV1=sV1,sV2=sV2,dist=dist,seed=b)
        fns=dict(ols=ols,rpiv=rpiv,sce=sce,ape=ape,oracle=oracle,
            gc=gaussian_copula,bmw=breitung_mw)
        for m in methods: res[m].append(fns[m](d))
    return {k:(np.nanmean(v),np.nanstd(v)) for k,v in res.items()}

# --- 4. Reproduce tables ---
print("Table: varying gamma1 (alpha2=0.8, n=2000, B=400)")
for g1 in [0.1,0.2,0.3,0.4,0.5,0.6,0.7,0.8,0.9]:
    r=mc(g1,0.8)
    print(f" g1={g1} ols={r['ols'][0]:.3f} "
        f"rpiv={r['rpiv'][0]:.3f} sce={r['sce'][0]:.3f}")

print("Table: varying alpha2 (gamma1=0.4, n=2000, B=400)")
for a2 in [0.1,0.2,0.3,0.4,0.5,0.6,0.7,0.8,0.9]:
    r=mc(0.4,a2)
    print(f" a2={a2} ols={r['ols'][0]:.3f} rpiv={r['rpiv'][0]:.3f}"
        f" sce={r['sce'][0]:.3f} ape={r['ape'][0]:.3f}")

```

```

print("Table: consistency (gamma1=0.4, alpha2=0.8, B=400)")
for n in [200,500,1000,2000,5000,10000]:
  r=mc(0.4,0.8,n=n)
  print(f" n={n} ols={r['ols'][0]:.4f} sce={r['sce'][0]:.4f}")

print("Table: recent methods (n=3000, B=400)")
meths=['ols','rpiv','sce','gc','bmw','oracle']
for dist in ['normal','chi2']:
  r=mc(0.4,0.8,n=3000,B=400,dist=dist,methods=meths)
  print(f" DGP={dist}")
  for m in meths:
    print(f" {m} mean={r[m][0]:.4f} "
          f"bias={100*(r[m][0]-0.4)/0.4:+.1f}%")

```

C R Code for Lewbel (1997) Cross-Validation

The Monte Carlo comparison between HME and [Lewbel \(1997\)](#) in Section 7.9 uses the official implementation `higherMomentsIV` from R package `REndo` ([REndo Package, 2024](#)). This appendix provides the R reproduction script.

```

# =====
# HME vs Lewbel (1997) via REndo::higherMomentsIV
# Reproduces Table 11 of the paper
# =====
library(REndo)
set.seed(42)

# --- 1. DGP under mediation, U skewed, V1/V2 symmetric ---
make_U <- function(n, dist) {
  if (dist == "beta_mild") U <- rbeta(n, 2, 5)
  if (dist == "beta_medium") U <- rbeta(n, 2, 8)
  if (dist == "lognormal") U <- rlnorm(n, 0, 0.5)
  if (dist == "chi2_3") U <- rchisq(n, df = 3)
  if (dist == "exponential") U <- rexp(n, rate = 1)
  (U - mean(U)) / sd(U)
}

gen_dgp <- function(n, dist, gamma1 = 0.4, alpha2 = 0.8, seed = NULL) {
  if (!is.null(seed)) set.seed(seed)
  U <- make_U(n, dist)
  V1 <- rnorm(n); V2 <- rnorm(n); X <- rnorm(n)
  e2 <- alpha2*U + V2
  e1 <- gamma1*alpha2*U + V1
  Y2 <- 0.3*X + e2
  Y1 <- 0.6*X + gamma1*Y2 + e1
  data.frame(Y1 = Y1, Y2 = Y2, X = X)
}

```

```

# --- 2. HME:  $\gamma_1 = 0.5 * (E[xi^3] / E[e2^3])^{(1/3)}$  ---
hme_r <- function(d) {
  xi <- residuals(lm(Y1 ~ X, data = d))
  e2h <- residuals(lm(Y2 ~ X, data = d))
  m3_xi <- mean(xi^3); m3_e2h <- mean(e2h^3)
  if (abs(m3_e2h) < 1e-6) return(NA_real_)
  ratio <- m3_xi / m3_e2h
  if (ratio <= 0) return(NA_real_)
  0.5 * sign(ratio) * abs(ratio)^(1/3)
}

# --- 3. Lewbel (1997) via REndo (unquoted symbols, NSE) ---
lewbels_yp <- function(d) {
  fit <- tryCatch(
    higherMomentsIV(Y1 ~ X + Y2 | Y2 | IIV(iiv = yp),
                    data = d, verbose = FALSE),
    error = function(e) NULL)
  if (is.null(fit)) NA_real_ else coef(fit)["Y2"]
}
lewbels_p2 <- function(d) {
  fit <- tryCatch(
    higherMomentsIV(Y1 ~ X + Y2 | Y2 | IIV(iiv = p2),
                    data = d, verbose = FALSE),
    error = function(e) NULL)
  if (is.null(fit)) NA_real_ else coef(fit)["Y2"]
}
lewbels_full <- function(d) {
  fit <- tryCatch(
    higherMomentsIV(Y1 ~ X + Y2 | Y2 |
                    IIV(iiv = yp) + IIV(iiv = p2) +
                    IIV(iiv = y2) + IIV(iiv = g, g = x2, X),
                    data = d, verbose = FALSE),
    error = function(e) NULL)
  if (is.null(fit)) NA_real_ else coef(fit)["Y2"]
}

# --- 4. Monte Carlo loop ---
run_mc <- function(dist, n = 5000, B = 200) {
  res <- data.frame(hme = numeric(B), yp = numeric(B),
                   p2 = numeric(B), full = numeric(B))
  for (b in 1:B) {
    d <- gen_dgp(n, dist, seed = b)
    res$hme[b] <- hme_r(d)
    res$yp[b] <- lewbels_yp(d)
    res$p2[b] <- lewbels_p2(d)
    res$full[b] <- lewbels_full(d)
  }
  data.frame(
    dist = dist,

```

```
HME      = round(mean(res$hme, na.rm = TRUE), 4),
Lewbel_yp= round(mean(res$yp,  na.rm = TRUE), 4),
Lewbel_p2= round(mean(res$p2,  na.rm = TRUE), 4),
Lewbel_full = round(mean(res$full, na.rm = TRUE), 4))
}

results <- do.call(rbind, lapply(
  c("beta_mild", "beta_medium", "lognormal",
    "chi2_3", "exponential"), run_mc))
print(results)
```